

Review

Mapping the use of ecological indicators across the marine research landscape: A global bibliometric analysis

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ABSTRACT

Marine ecological indicators are essential tools for evaluating environmental status and guiding sustainable management, yet their use in scientific literature varies widely. To synthesize the extensive research involving ecological indicators, interpret thematic and regional trends and highlight major gaps, we conducted a bibliometric analysis of 6828 scientific publications retrieved from SCOPUS from 1955 to 2025. Publications increased exponentially over time, and originated mostly from North America, China, and Western Europe, with fewer contributions from North and Central Africa. A term-clustering analysis identified four main research areas: a) marine ecosystem attributes and sustainable management; b) community composition and structure; c) benthic ecosystems and related indices; and d) environmental pollution and contamination. Publication and citation rates per cluster show a clear shift from descriptive studies towards applied ecology and conservation-focused research. Finally, most of the international collaborations leading to the publications of our dataset link back to the aforementioned high-publishing regions, highlighting the need to promote a more balanced global scientific participation to tackle global and regional needs. Our findings validate the need to move towards evidence-based management and conservation planning, which require the development and application of integrative, ecosystem-level indicators that can translate complex environmental data into reliable measures of ecosystem health and functioning. Effective, systematic monitoring tools can accelerate the operationalization of such indicators. However, emerging technologies (including automated monitoring systems and molecular approaches) are currently underrepresented in the literature and offer unprecedented opportunities to support informed, adaptive conservation strategies under ongoing anthropogenic pressures.

1. Introduction

Since the early settlements in coastal environments, marine ecosystems have been fundamental for the survival and prosperity of human populations (Brown and Peters, 2019). Briefly, they are a source of food and other natural resources (Steele, 1974), protect coastal integrity (McLean et al., 2001), help regulate climate (Doney et al., 2012), facilitate nutrient cycling (Herbert, 1999), and provide cultural services (e.g., tourism and recreational activities; Beaumont et al., 2007). However, the pressures they have been facing, including climate change, overexploitation, plastic and chemical pollution, among others, have been ever increasing, especially after the industrial revolution, and moving further offshore and towards deeper waters (Danovaro et al.,

2008; Coll et al., 2010). The effects of this expansion and intensification of human activity, including habitat degradation, biodiversity loss, stock plummeting and food web structural degradation, are not always well documented, nor is their cumulative impact always fully understood (Simeoni et al., 2023).

Given their importance, pressures and impacts faced, the pressing need to detect and monitor these changes to implement effective mitigation or reversing strategies has been recognized by individual nations, as well as by several European and Global legislative bodies promoting conservation actions (European Commission, 2013; European Commission, 2019; Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación, 2020). Most of these actions rely on the accuracy and efficiency of indicators (here referring to “a quantitative or qualitative measure to

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estimate the current state and future trends of physical, chemical, biological, or socio-economic conditions of an environment” (Fisher, 2001), to transform data on monitored marine ecosystems to informative knowledge (Prosekov et al., 2020; Borja, 2014).

In the International landscape, the Convention on Biological Diversity (Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), 1992) set the Aichi Biodiversity Targets; however, in some cases, no specific marine indicator has been identified. The European Union adopted in 2008 the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD 2008/56/EC) (European Commission, 2026), which mandates the assessment of the state of Europe's seas and aims to achieve or maintain Good Environmental Status (GES). In line with the MSFD, the contracting parties of the Regional Sea Conventions are required to set criteria to achieve GES across their respective seas: the Mediterranean Sea under the Barcelona Convention (UNEP, 1976) (United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), 1976), the Northeast Atlantic Ocean under the OSPAR Convention (OSPAR Commission, 1992), and the Baltic Sea under the HELCOM Convention (Helsinki Commission (HELCOM), 1992).

More recently, marine ecosystems formed part of the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs; United Nations, 2015), in particular SDG14 “Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, sea and marine resources for sustainable development”. Recalling several of these Agenda 2030 objectives, in 2019 the UN Member States declared 2021–2030 to be the “UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration” (United Nations General Assembly, 2021). The resolution encourages countries to develop and implement measures to prevent degradation, enhance scientific research and scale up good practices reinforcing existing restoration initiatives. At the European Union level, the Nature Restoration Law (European Commission, 2024) was adopted in June 2024, which defines a framework for Member States to implement restoration measures by 2050. Beyond legislation, international research networks have proposed complementary monitoring frameworks, such as restored ecosystem attributes (Society for Ecological Restoration (SER), 2004), Essential Ocean Variables (Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), 2025), and Essential Biodiversity Variables (Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), 2025).

Given the intrinsic breadth and complexity of ecological indicators, both in terms of conceptual definitions and of practical approaches and real-life applications, they appear in a wide body of marine scientific literature. Thus, we conducted a bibliometric literature review (Donthu et al., 2021), to systematically organize and synthesize research involving marine ecological indicators. In particular, we analyzed a large volume of scientific publications from the last 70 years, integrating both temporal (i.e., year of publication) and spatial (i.e., country leading the publication) information. Specifically, we comprehensively mapped published research on either marine ecological indicators per se (e.g., theoretical development or practical testing and validation), or with marine ecological indicator contribution (e.g., conservation applications or scientific case studies), to: a) depict the main marine research domains involving marine ecological indicator uses, and links between them; b) assess marine ecological indicator involvement in these domains evolved across the decades, as new themes emerged; c) analyze the geographical distribution of research efforts to highlight regional contributions and international collaborations; and d) identify and verify current knowledge gaps among the established themes.

2. Material and methods

All the available relevant scientific literature (i.e., journal articles, conference proceedings and book chapters) was retrieved from the SCOPUS database on October 31st and used for scientific mapping, following Costa et al. (2020). Publications were selected using words and word strings in the title (TITLE), abstract (ABS) and keywords (KEY). The specific search query was:

TITLE-ABS-KEY ((marine) AND (ecological) AND (indicator* OR index OR indices)).

Where TITLE-ABS-KEY is a combined field that limits the search to titles, abstracts and keywords; AND is a logical operator indicating that the results have to include all words even if they are semantically far apart; OR is a logical operator indicating that articles that contain any of the words are to be retrieved; and * indicates that words of interest include any modification of the stated initial part of a keyword. The retrieved documents were manually validated by checking titles and then abstracts, eliminating out-of-scope instances. Finally, all documents were extracted as a .csv file for subsequent analysis (see Supplementary Material S1). The bibliometric analysis of the marine ecological indicators research landscape has been conducted utilizing VOSviewer software (version 1.6.20, van Eck and Waltman, 2010). Complementary data processing and visualization were performed in the R statistical Language (version 4.5.0, R Core Team, 2025).

2.1. Publications trend

A descriptive analysis of publications volume in the field of marine ecological indicators was carried out. To account for the fact that data for 2025 only cover the first ten months of the year, a normalization procedure was applied. Specifically, for the years from 1955 to 2024, the total number of publications was divided by 12, while for 2025, it was divided by 10. This yielded a monthly publication rate for each year.

2.2. Global distribution of publications

Since the .csv file extracted from SCOPUS provides information on the postal addresses of institutions, we also perform a geocoding analysis using the Geocoding script from the CorText digital platform (<http://www.cortext.net>). This process involves converting text-based descriptions of locations, such as institutional addresses, into geographic coordinates. The geocoding procedure enabled the identification of specific locations at both city and country scales. The output file (see Supplementary Material S2) was then imported into R to generate a map visualizing the global distribution of publications, with countries colored according to the associated research effort, measured as the total number of documents. In addition, a second map was produced with a geographic focus on Europe to highlight regional patterns more clearly.

2.3. International collaborations

To analyze international collaboration patterns (Matos et al., 2018), we exported the output of the clustering analysis (i.e., co-occurrence links between countries) from VOSviewer as a .json file. We then processed it in R to generate a Chord Diagram representing the international collaboration network at the country level, grouped by geographical region. To ensure readability and interpretability of the diagram, we selected the countries applying the Elbow Method.

2.4. Term clustering analysis

The SCOPUS .csv was imported into VOSviewer and a thesaurus file was generated (see Supplementary Material S3) to facilitate data cleaning (i.e., merge different synonyms, abbreviations with full forms, different spellings, etc.). At the same time, this allowed us to exclude terms with little or no relevance to this study (e.g., too generic, dates, methodology-related, etc.). Then, we set the threshold for inclusion of terms in subsequent analyses to a minimum of $n = 20$ occurrences (“binary counting” method; i.e., number of documents in which a term occurs at least once, to avoid cluttering with less meaningful terms and associations). Filtered text data were distributed in a map of thematic clusters (“term clustering map”), with distances being inversely proportional to the common occurrence of terms in publications' titles and abstracts. VOSviewer algorithms minimize the difference between association strength and distance between term pairs (Klarin, 2024). Terms in the map are visualized as labelled bubbles of proportional size

to each term's weight (i.e., its number of occurrences). Bubbles are connected with lines of proportional thickness to the strength of their connection (i.e., the number of publications where two connected terms co-occur). To improve the clarity in the visualization, only the 300 strongest lines are shown in the maps.

The thematic clusters in the term clustering map are used as proxies for established or emerging research areas (Costa et al., 2020; Aguzzi et al., 2023). The different colors represent distinct clusters, each interpreted to correspond to a specific family of research topics. The total number of clusters is determined by a “resolution parameter” (i.e., lower resolution leads to fewer clusters, while higher resolution results in more). Based on the total number of terms and after experimenting with different options, the resolution parameter was set to 0.9, yielding the most suitable level of detail for subsequent analysis and interpretation. For further specifications of the VOSviewer clustering technique, refer to van Eck and Waltman (2010) and Waltman et al. (2010).

2.5. Temporal analysis per term and cluster

We used the monthly publication rate for each year (see 2.1 above) as inverse weights and calculated the weighted average and median year of publication of the documents where each term occurred. This approach was selected to moderate the bias towards recent years, with exponentially more publications across the entire field (see Results below). In addition, we fitted a Bayesian multinomial logistic regression model to quantify the potential differences in the representation of the different clusters along the years of the study. The model is formally described in Eq. (1).

$$\log \frac{p_{t,j}}{p_{t,j'}} = \beta_{0,j} + \beta_{1,j} \times \text{Year}_t \quad (1)$$

where p corresponds to the probability of occurrence for cluster j compared to the total occurrences J (i.e., for all clusters) in Year t , with a weighted likelihood via the observed occurrences $\text{Count}_{t,j}$.

Moderately informed priors were used for intercepts $\beta_{0,j} \sim T(3, 0, 2.5)$ and slopes $\beta_{1,j} \sim N(0,1)$. The model was fitted with 4 Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) chains of 3000 iterations each (1000 warm-up that do not count in the final result and 2000 sampling, resulting in a total of 8000 useful iterations per model). The convergence of the MCMC chains was assessed through the \hat{R} metric (Gelman and Rubin, 1992), while Effective Sample Sizes (ESS) were used to assess their efficiency. Evidence against the null hypothesis for each individual coefficient was tested by calculating Bayes Factors (Savage-Dickey density ratio; Kass and Raftery, 1995; Wagenmakers et al., 2010). Model fitting was performed with the R package “brms” (v. 2.22.0; Bürkner, 2017) and Bayes Factors were calculated with the R package “bayestestR” (v. 0.17.0; Makowski et al., 2019).

2.6. Term average citation map analysis

We generated a “term average citation map” that shows the average normalized number of citations received by the documents in which a term occurs. The color gradient represents this score, going from blue (minimum score) to yellow (maximum score). The score is adjusted by dividing the number of citations by the average number of citations in the same year to avoid biases related to publication age, as older works typically accumulate more citations. To evaluate potential differences in citations among the clusters, we conducted a Kruskal-Wallis non-parametric test, accompanied by Mann-Whitney test with post hoc Bonferroni correction for pairwise comparisons.

3. Results

The search from the SCOPUS database produced a total of 6828 documents, spanning from 1955 to 2025.

3.1. Spatiotemporal trends and distributions of publications

The temporal trend in publications from 1955 to 2025 (Fig. 1) reveals an exponential growth. During the initial decades, scientific output was minimal, with fewer than five publications per year. However, starting around 2000, there has been a marked and continuous increase in the number of publications, reaching over 200 documents in 2015 and 694 publications in 2024.

The global distribution of publications (Fig. 2a) shows that research on marine ecological indicators is conducted worldwide, with a predominance of publications from North America, China and Europe, and fewer from North and Central Africa. The European publication map (Fig. 2b) reveals a marked concentration of scientific output in Western and Northern Europe.

3.2. International collaborations

The Chord Diagram (Fig. 3) visualizes the international collaborations among the most active countries in marine ecological indicator research, with each country depicted as a segment of the circular plot. The links between countries indicate the collaborations. Countries are color-coded according to their continental affiliation (Europe in blue, North America in green, South America in red, Asia in yellow, Oceania in pink, Africa in orange).

There is a high density of links between European countries, indicating a high level of European collaboration. Furthermore, the diagram highlights a considerable collaboration between the United States and several European countries. Australia and New Zealand show stronger collaborative ties with the United States and the United Kingdom, whereas Asian countries appear to collaborate predominantly with European countries and the United States.

3.3. Term map analyses

A total of 195 terms are displayed in the “term clustering map” (Fig. 4), as well as in the subsequent ones. We identified four distinct conceptual clusters, which overlapped only partially: a) marine ecosystems attributes and sustainable management (in red, 83 terms), b) community composition and structure (in green, 52 terms), c) benthic ecosystems and related indices (in blue, 27 terms), and d) environmental pollution and contamination (in yellow, 33 terms).

The red cluster includes terms related to marine ecosystem health/attributes, sustainable management and conservation. Indeed, terms like *ecological function*, *food web*, *fish community* emerge as core elements. Moreover, terms associated with conservation actions, with terms like *marine protected area*, *conservation*, *management strategy* stand out.

The green cluster focuses on methods and metrics for assessing ecosystem health. It includes traditional terms such as *species diversity*, *community structure*, *Pielou index*, *Shannon index*.

The blue cluster includes several terms specifically related to the benthic environment, including *benthic community*, *benthic macrofauna*, and associated metrics. Among the terms, *AMBI* and *BOPA* are indices that have been widely applied and validated across multiple biogeographic regions and under different types of environmental pressures (ICES, 2022).

Finally, there is the yellow cluster. It is primarily made by terms concerning research efforts aimed at studying the environmental pollution and contamination (e.g., *contamination*, *bioaccumulation*, *microplastic*, *pollution index* among others).

The “term average citation map” (Fig. 5) reveals that the cluster “environmental pollution and contamination” is associated with a high normalized citation score, as indicated by the predominance of yellow-colored terms. This cluster indeed shows the highest mean value (1.6), followed by the cluster “marine ecosystems functioning and sustainable management” (1.0), the cluster “benthic ecosystems and related indices” (0.9) and the cluster “community composition and structure” (0.8).

Fig. 1. Trend of publications in marine ecological indicators research. Bars indicate the annual publication rate, expressed as the number of publications per month for each year from 1955 to 2025, as extracted from SCOPUS.

Fig. 2. Geographic distribution of the publications on marine ecological indicators research (1955–2025) on a global (a) and European (b) level. The color gradient represents publication intensity, with red indicating high numbers of publications, blue intermediate, and white very low. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

3.4. Statistical analyses

The weighted metrics for the year of publication of each term showed a progressive shift from the blue cluster “benthic ecosystems and related indices”, through the red “marine ecosystem attributes and sustainable management” and green “community composition and structure” clusters and finally, towards the yellow cluster “environmental pollution and contamination”. The complete list containing the weighted means and medians for all terms is presented in Supplementary Material S5.

The multinomial logistic regression model converged without apparent issues ($\hat{R} = 1$ with values < 1.05 considered acceptable), while both Bulk and Tail ESS were sufficient to trust the model outcomes (approx. 3000 to 4000 for each coefficient). Bayes Factors for all clusters showed decisive evidence (i.e., values < 0.01 or > 100 for negative and positive differences, respectively) against the null hypothesis of no statistical difference. Fig. 6 presents the temporal changes in the observed proportions of the occurrence of terms belonging to each cluster, as well as the occurrence probabilities as predicted by the model. The complete output of the model is presented in Supplementary Material S6).

For the “term citation map”, the Kruskal–Wallis test rejected the null

hypothesis of equal medians among the clusters ($p = 2.096 \times 10^{-7}$). Pairwise comparisons (see Supplementary Material S7) using the Mann–Whitney test with Bonferroni correction revealed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between most clusters, except between the red and blue clusters, and between the green and blue clusters, for which no statistically significant difference was observed.

4. Discussion

This study provides a systematic overview of the global literature with contributions of on marine ecological indicators, using a bibliometric approach to map the current organization and future perspectives of marine ecological indicator-related research. In particular, we analyzed the thematic structure of the literature using term map clustering. The analysis reveals four major clusters of terms that describe the global orientation and status of ecological indicators in the field of marine research: a) marine ecosystem attributes and sustainable management; b) community composition and structure; c) benthic ecosystems and related indices; and d) environmental pollution and contamination. The temporal evolution of publication rates shows an

Fig. 3. Chord diagram of international collaborations in marine ecological indicator research. The 40 most productive countries are shown as segments, with chords indicating co-authorship links between countries. Segment and chord colors denote continental affiliation: Europe (blue), North America (green), South America (red), Asia (yellow), Oceania (pink), and Africa (orange). Country codes (ISO-3) are the following: Europe: BEL (Belgium), DNK (Denmark), FIN (Finland), FRA (France), DEU (Germany), GRC (Greece), ITA (Italy), NLD (Netherlands), NOR (Norway), POL (Poland), PRT (Portugal), ESP (Spain), SWE (Sweden), TUR (Turkey), GBR (United Kingdom); North America: CAN (Canada), MEX (Mexico), USA (United States); South America: ARG (Argentina), BRA (Brazil), CHL (Chile), GUY (Guyana); Asia: CHN (China), IND (India), IDN (Indonesia), IRN (Iran), JPN (Japan), MYS (Malaysia), PAK (Pakistan), PHL (Philippines), VNM (Vietnam), HKG (Hong Kong); Oceania: AUS (Australia), NZL (New Zealand); Africa: CIV (Côte d'Ivoire), NGA (Nigeria), ZAF (South Africa), SDN (Sudan), ZWE (Zimbabwe); Russia: RUS (Russian Federation). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

exponential increase since the early 2000s, indicating growing global attention and ongoing expansion of the use of indicators in the field of marine research. The spatial analysis demonstrates a global interest in the subject, although some regions remain underrepresented and the existing collaboration links are uneven.

4.1. Established and emerging areas of marine ecological indicator research

The term map analysis (see Fig. 4) highlighted four major thematic domains that structure the contribution of marine ecological indicators. The first cluster (i.e., the red one in Fig. 4) focuses on marine ecosystem components and processes, as well as their management. This cluster includes terms such as *ecological function*, *food web*, *fish community*, *size class*, and *functional group*, which relate to the biological and functional components. At the same time, the recurrence of terms associated with conservation actions, such as *marine protected area*, *conservation*, *restoration*, *sustainable fishery* and *management strategy*, highlights a clear and

widespread effort to enhance the management of marine ecosystems by incorporating ecological dynamics (Tam et al., 2017). The close connection of these terms underscores a shared recognition of the need to move towards a more holistic environmental management approach that accounts for the various interactions and processes within an ecosystem, instead of focusing solely on resource-specific approaches (Link, 2005).

This is the core principle behind the Ecosystem-Based Management (EBM) strategy (Rosenberg and McLeod, 2005), the full-scale operationalization of which appears to be still in development (Cormier et al., 2017; Manea et al., 2020; Stelzenmüller et al., 2020), as shown by the relatively more recent surge of the red cluster terms compared to the more traditional approaches represented in the green and blue ones (see Fig. 6 and Supplementary Material S5 on publication years for clusters and individual terms, respectively).

Closely positioned and linked to the red cluster, the green one (see Fig. 4) is more oriented towards approaches and metrics used to describe community composition and structure, including widely applied

Fig. 4. Term map analysis for publications from 1955 to 2025. The 4 highlighted clusters represent key established and emerging topics in marine ecological indicators research. Each cluster is color-coded to distinguish the terms associated with different thematic areas. For visual clarity, only a selection of terms is displayed; the complete list is available in the Supplementary Material S4.

ecological indices such as those indicated by the terms *Species Richness*, *Shannon index*, and *Pielou index*. The common characteristic of these indicators is that they are easy to calculate from a community matrix, corresponding to Hill's numbers of successive orders (Hill, 1973; Chao and Ricotta, 2019). However, being descriptive and mainly based on a small set of variables and metrics (e.g., taxa presence, individual counts, and surface cover; Dunham et al., 2024), they fail to account for the functional integrity of marine ecosystems which requires more complex metrics, explicitly linked to ecosystem processes (de Juan et al., 2015; Okey, 2018; Bonilla-Valencia et al., 2022). This is reflected in Fig. 6 by their asynchronous appearance compared to the function-related terms of the red cluster. The absence of a widely accepted conceptual framework for applying functional indicators (Mason and de Bello, 2013; Mammola et al., 2021; Schmera et al., 2023) is also consistent with the absence of a distinct, clearly-defined cluster in our term map. Finally, the green cluster also comprises molecular approaches, as shown by the terms *metabarcoding*, *DNA*, and *eDNA*, suggesting the close correlation between traditional and molecular ecology sampling approaches which can complement each other in the common goal of expanding the detected biodiversity across a broader range of species (Danovaro et al., 2020).

The third cluster (i.e., the blue one in Fig. 4) is dedicated specifically to benthic communities, reflecting their suitability for use as indicators of changes in ecosystem quality (Dauer, 1993). Indeed, macrobenthic assemblages are among the most frequently used biological indicators in European monitoring frameworks (van Hoey et al., 2010; Smit et al., 2021), potentially due to their limited mobility making them easier to quantify in space and time than mobile pelagic fauna. Likewise, they may respond sensitively to changes in local environmental conditions (Bilyard, 1987; Warwick, 1993), providing reliable insights into disturbances (Salen-Picard et al., 1997). Notable reference registries

include AMBI (Borja et al., 2000) and BOPA (Dauvin and Ruellet, 2007). While AMBI focuses on the response of different soft-bottom invertebrate macrofauna to a wide range of disturbances, BOPA uses opportunistic polychaetes and amphipods as benchmarks for the levels of environmental stress. Contrary to the generic community indicators from the green cluster, these reflect the specific response of communities to stressors (even if some aspects such as functional traits can be missed), and can complement more targeted approaches to provide a more complete and reliable benthic assessment (Lu et al., 2021; van Denderen et al., 2024).

Finally, the last cluster (i.e., the yellow one in Fig. 4) groups publications on ecotoxicology and anthropogenic contamination, mirroring the growing attention of scientific research towards the effects of pollutants such as heavy metals and microplastics. The presence of terms such as *pollution index*, *contamination level*, and *bioaccumulation* points to a shared awareness of the need to develop and apply quantitative metrics to assess the state of the environment, including pollution level, as well as for harmonized sampling and reporting methods (Islam and Tanaka, 2004; Brown and Takada, 2017; Fossi et al., 2020; Parolini et al., 2023; Williams et al., 2023).

The overall clustering structure identified in this study reveals a notable asymmetry: the red cluster is broad and conceptually heterogeneous, while the other clusters are more technical and focused on specific tools and metrics. The co-occurrence network reveals that EBM-related terminology in the literature gravitates around broad conceptual themes (conservation, ecological function, management strategy) rather than around the operational elements required for its implementation. This result quantitatively supports the existing literature on the conceptual dominance but rather weak operationalization of EBM in terms of both indicator development and applications. For instance, Papadopoulou et al. (2025) draw a distinction between EBM principles

Fig. 6. Temporal change in term cluster frequencies. The upper panel (bar plot) represents observed proportions of terms, while the lower panel (line plot) contains term occurrence probabilities predicted by the model. The color patterns match the ones from the term clustering map. The year of the first observed occurrence for each cluster is used as the starting point for the predictions.

KM3NeT, among others), providing a constant flow of multidisciplinary biological, geochemical, and oceanographic data (Matabos et al., 2016; Scherwath et al., 2019; Trowbridge et al., 2019; Aguzzi et al., 2021).

At the same time, as awareness and concerns rose, conservation measures entered the picture and began to get integrated into adaptive management strategies (Ramirez-Llodra et al., 2011). For example, conservation tools such as Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) are conceived not only as zones for biodiversity conservation (Hays et al., 2020; Pettersen et al., 2021; Rodríguez-Rodríguez and Martínez-Vega, 2022) but also as policy instruments for the sustainable management of marine resources (Rice et al., 2012; OECD, 2017; Dave, 2025). The growing integration of technology and management is giving rise to new ways of running new adaptive management strategies, where continuously updated monitoring data are used to adjust regulations on major areas of human impact (FAO, 2020; Hilborn et al., 2020). This is ensuring that fish stocks and other resources are used responsibly, while also engaging local fishing communities (Santín et al., 2022).

More recent literature highlights research on contamination, likely reflecting the growing global concern regarding pollutants such as heavy metals, microplastics, and persistent organic compounds (Zhu et al., 2024; Adeleye et al., 2024). This cluster also shows the highest normalized citation scores (see Fig. 5), suggesting that this topic is having a notable scientific relevance and influence nowadays. Over the past two decades, global awareness of marine pollution has risen sharply, driven by public debate and international regulatory frameworks. Conventions such as MARPOL 73/78 (International Maritime Organization, 1973), which aims to minimize operational and accidental pollution by shipping, and the Stockholm Convention on

Persistent Organic Pollutants (2001), a global treaty to protect human health and the environment from POPs, have provided a policy backbone for monitoring and reducing contaminants in marine ecosystems. Major pollution crises have also acted as catalysts: the Deepwater Horizon oil spill in 2010, for example, led to extensive investigations into the effects of hydrocarbons on pelagic and benthic communities, including the use of coral and deep-sea assemblages as indicators of ecosystem-level impacts (Fisher et al., 2014; Girard et al., 2018). Finally, advances in analytical and molecular technologies (e.g., high-resolution mass spectrometry and biomarker analyses) have enabled the detection and quantification of pollutants with unprecedented precision, expanding research possibilities (Hollender et al., 2019). Recent terms such as “molecular approaches”, including metabarcoding and rRNA gene, highlight the emergence of novel techniques that can complement traditional sampling (i.e., trawling) and acoustic and imaging methods (Giroux et al., 2022).

Apart from the conceptual focus, this stage succession trend also aligns with the increasing adoption of the Drivers–Pressures–State–Impact–Response (DPSIR) framework (Smeets and Weterings, 1999) in interdisciplinary indicator development, model conceptualization, and structuring policy-relevant research (Svarstad et al., 2008). Our results suggest a transition from the occurrence “state” indicators (e.g., diversity indices, consistent with the descriptive nature of research in the mid-20 century) towards terminology related to “pressures” (e.g., *overfishing* and *fishing effort*) and “impact” (e.g., *acidification*, *habitat loss*, and *contamination*). On the other hand, specific indicators of “response” are not highlighted, although policy responses do emerge (e.g., *Marine Protected Area*, *restoration*, *Marine Spatial Planning*, etc.). Nevertheless, they do not appear as a structurally cohesive cluster in the maps, showing the current discord in the broad application of a unified management framework (Patrício et al., 2016), even though several studies have attempted to streamline it (Gari et al., 2015).

4.3. Geographic trends in marine ecological indicators

Marine ecological indicators contribute to research effort on a global scale, although the majority of studies are concentrated in Europe, North America, Australia and China (see Fig. 2). However, regions such as Africa, Central and South America and Middle Asia are markedly underrepresented in the literature landscape. This underrepresentation could be likely attributed to factors such as political instability, which can limit access to research funding and reduce opportunities for international collaborations (Achieng et al., 2023). Moreover, in these regions the universities and research institutions have started contributing to this field only in recent years (Ciocca and Delgado, 2017). Consequently, it is important to take into account that areas with extensive research activity often dominate the development and validation of indicators, potentially biasing commonly used indicators towards the ecological contexts of well-studied regions and reducing transferability to data-poor ones.

The geographic imbalance can be treated as a part of a broader asymmetry between the Global North and South in the production of marine knowledge and in participation in global policy processes (e.g., WOA, IPCC or IPBES). This creates a vicious cycle in which limited scientific capacity in southern countries leads to less locally produced research, weaker representation in science-diplomacy reports and, ultimately, policies that are poorly aligned with the priorities of marginalized contexts (Polejack et al., 2025). Recent work on equity and justice in ocean sciences (de Vos et al., 2023) highlights how “parachute science” (or neocolonial science) and unbalanced North-South partnerships can marginalize local expertise and limit the development of research led by scientists from under-resourced regions.

This observed imbalance has direct implications for the design and application of indicator-based monitoring frameworks and for the ambition to achieve globally relevant marine ecosystem management. Collaborative efforts can help bridge this gap by providing access to

resources and expertise. The importance of such collaborations becomes even more evident given the limited research links detected between the industrialized countries and the developing ones (see Fig. 3). As highlighted by Roch et al. (2025), fostering more equitable science would require concrete measures such as building long-term and trust-based partnerships and prioritizing funding for researchers in low-income countries. A step forward in this direction is the recent EU calls (Horizon Europe) in which Asian, African and South American countries, among others, are eligible for direct funding within European consortia. Finally, the ambitions of the UN Decade of Ocean Science, particularly Outcome 6 “an accessible ocean” (Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission, 2021) offer a framework to address these inequalities through the transfer of marine technologies, capacity-development programs and interoperable data infrastructures.

4.4. Identified research gaps in indicators research and future perspectives

Despite substantial growth in research on or involving marine ecological indicators, significant gaps remain (Han et al., 2020; Kahlert et al., 2020; Muhl et al., 2022), including: a) operationalizing the use of marine ecological indicators in monitoring frameworks, b) establishing long-term observation systems that capture temporal dynamics, c) achieving broad spatial coverage at local and regional scales, and d) integrating multiparametric datasets that encompass biological, chemical, and physical dimensions.

Extensive literature assesses the suitability and performance of ecological indicators (e.g., Muxika et al., 2005; Shin et al., 2010; Teixeira et al., 2016; Smit et al., 2021; Pinna et al., 2023, among others), and several indices (e.g., AMBI, BOPA) have been formally integrated in European legislation (incl. WFD and MSFD). However, terminology relevant to the operational frameworks that would reflect a global effort to adopt standardized, coherent measures, such as Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs; Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), 2025), Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs; Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network (GEO BON), 2025) or the MSFD GES descriptors is strikingly absent from the thematic structure evidenced by our results. This provides quantitative evidence to support the argument that full operationalization of marine ecological indicators is still in development (indicatively; Proença et al., 2017; Kissling et al., 2018; Jetz et al., 2019; von Schuckmann et al., 2026).

Indeed, the practical application of indicators often requires specialized expertise and labor-intensive sampling (Borja et al., 2013). Moreover, while several indicators have been validated for coastal waters, they require further evaluation in other bathymetric zones and habitat types (e.g., deep-sea environments), where accessibility, sampling effort, and taxonomic resolution are strongly constrained (Raicevich et al., 2025). Their applicability is also limited by the need to define habitat- and depth-specific reference conditions (Bald et al., 2005; Christiansen et al., 2022). Establishing such baselines, particularly in the deep sea, remains problematic, as pristine or minimally disturbed reference sites are increasingly rare. The absence of such baseline information arises because scientific exploration started later (and never caught up with the rate) than human exploitation (Borja et al., 2013; Holman et al., 2025).

As widely recognized in the literature (García-García et al., 2019; Painting et al., 2020), establishing long-term observation systems, achieving broad spatial coverage, and integrating multiparametric datasets, constitute major challenges in marine ecological monitoring. Our bibliometric analysis provides quantitative evidence of a critical aspect: the limited integration of emerging technologies in marine research in conjunction with applied ecological indicator framework, therefore highlighting an important yet underutilized opportunity to overcome these limitations (Rubbens et al., 2023; Butt and Hamid, 2025; Ucciero et al., 2026). ROVs and AUVs already enable surveys across broad spatial scales, while landers and Internet Operated Vehicles (IOVs), including benthic crawlers, provide long-term, high-frequency,

multiparametric data (Robison et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2021; Chatzievangelou et al., 2022; Fogliani and Grande, 2023; Aguzzi et al., 2024). Another promising detection tool are neutrino telescopes, which, although primarily designed for astrophysical research, can gather multiparametric data in deep-sea environments, complementing data collection by other ongoing field surveys and providing novel insights into ecosystem conditions across variable geographic and temporal scales (Adrián Martínez et al., 2016; Agostini et al., 2020). Despite the rapid development of these advanced monitoring technologies, they remain only marginally represented in the literature, as reflected by the absence of technology-related terms in the identified thematic clusters.

This technological expansion for ecological monitoring is presently being applied in the framework of relevant EU restoration actions in deep-sea MPAs in the context of ongoing Horizon Europe actions (e.g., REDRESS, <https://redress-project.eu/>; (REDRESS Project, 2026) BLUE CONNECT, <https://blueconnect-project.eu/>; (BLUE CONNECT Project, 2026) BioProtect, <https://bioprotect-project.eu/>, (BioProtect Project, 2026) among others). The constraints of monitoring marine systems are being further overcome by shifting from vessel-based to autonomous robotic platforms capable of multiparametric biological and environmental data collection. Innovations in marine robotics now integrate AI-driven algorithms to enable long-term, high-resolution observations without direct human intervention. This transition is strongly supported by current EU initiatives under the Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030” (European Commission, 2021), which envisages a networked, reliable, and persistent ocean-monitoring infrastructure. In parallel, the management, integration, and analysis of large-scale ecological data require robust digital infrastructures, a challenge addressed by the EU Digital Framework Agenda in the form of EDITO (European Digital Twin of the Ocean; Directorate-General for Research, and Innovation, European Commission, 2024), which supports the accurate and dynamic virtual representation of the marine ecosystem for modelling. Despite their potential, these technological approaches have not yet been systematically integrated into protocols for the monitoring of marine systems (and thus for the development of new ecological indicators or the broader application of existing ones), highlighting a critical area for future research.

All in all, our analyses showed how the ecological indicators have been utilized in marine research, the main application areas and how these dynamics changed over time. Even though our specific focus is not on assessing indicator quality, our interpretations were built on the criteria and benchmarks previously set in established and recent literature (Niemi and McDonald, 2004; von Schuckmann et al., 2026). It is thus plausible that, based on the existing body of work, commonly used marine ecological indicators that endured in time shared many of these characteristics including (among others):

- Scientific validity and accurate depiction of state
- Sensitivity and responsiveness to change
- Predictability and consistency
- Feasibility of calculation and cost-effectiveness
- Applicability over broad scales
- Straightforward interpretation and integration to management and policy protocols
- Accessibility on a regular basis
- Conceptual justification

Although most of the scientific components are well-developed and validated, the logistics of widely applying integrative, complex indicators remain an obstacle. Channeling marine indicator research towards combining these attributes with the evolving, technologically advanced monitoring protocols, will support holistic, integrated ocean management initiatives.

4.5. Study limitations

Here we used a bibliometric analysis that identifies terms commonly appearing in scientific literature together with ecological indicators. This method can be used to create thematic clusters based on the co-occurrence of terms extracted from the titles, abstracts and keywords of published literature with the terms defined in the query. As such, our approach is not focusing solely on research on marine ecological indicators, but rather on an expanded body of marine research in which marine ecological indicators contribute. This can include, for instance, literature on conservation of marine resources, habitats or ecosystem functions, as well as basic research case-studies. In these cases, marine ecological indicators can be used as a tool to quantify information, validate protocols, or as a target (e.g., development of technologies or sampling approaches that can assist in the calculation of specific indicators). Therefore, our work does not directly assess what makes a good marine ecological indicator, and its scope is not to precisely present the evolution of research focused strictly on marine ecological indicator development. Similarly, our analysis is intended to support the findings of existing literature that has identified specific gaps in marine ecological indicator research, and not to provide them as a direct, result-based output. Finally, since we have used a threshold in VOSviewer to filter the output of the SCOPUS query, there can be an inherent bias towards terms utilized in the period of higher publication rates (i.e., after the 1990s, especially in the last two decades). Terms appearing mostly in the early period of the study, might have failed to clear this threshold and have been thus excluded from the analyses.

5. Conclusions

This bibliometric review provides a quantitative synthesis of the global literature involving marine ecological indicators. Research focus has progressively shifted from descriptive metrics to more applied scenarios, to support ecosystem management, conservation, and policy-making during the last 70 years. Despite the growing body of research involving marine ecological indicators, significant gaps remain in operationalizing indicators, integrating technological advances, and ensuring global representativeness. To date, the most prominently used indicators are characterized by straightforward application, narrow taxonomic or habitat focus. Future research should prioritize co-developing or adapting indicators within long-term, automated monitoring infrastructures, taking advantage of the reduced cost of repetitive data collection they offer to enhance holistic, integrative approaches. Finally, international collaboration must be strengthened to reduce geographic bias and promote equitable knowledge sharing.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

F.M. Cecchini: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **P. Espina:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **S. Violino:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **C. Costa:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **J. Aguzzi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Conceptualization. **D. Chatzievangelou:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT in order to check for spelling errors and verify whether references were cited in the text and reference list. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2026.114984>.

Data availability

all data are available in the manuscript and supplementary materials

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